

AQUASERV

Research services
for **sustainable aquaculture,**
fisheries and **blue economy**

Services catalogue 1

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Access programme of the AQUASERV project. It analyses the background of the service catalogues of the project's contributing Research Infrastructures and partners and proposes the first AQUASERV catalogue of services.

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Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	5
2. Introduction	5
2.1. Background.....	5
2.2. Aim of the deliverable.....	5
2.3. The Catalogue and the Access System	6
2.4. Updates of the catalogue and next versions	6
3. Description of work.....	6
3.1. Analysis of the existing services catalogues	7
3.2. Grouping of similar services.....	8
3.3. Organization of services in categories and sub-categories	9
3.4. Revision of the vocabulary to fit a “service-based” approach	9
3.5. Final revision of the catalogue.....	10
4. Conclusions.....	11
4.1. Next steps.....	11
5. Appendices.....	12
5.1. Appendix 1 - Catalogue of services of AQUAEXCEL3.0.....	12
5.2. Appendix 2 - Catalogue of services of EMBRC.....	14
5.3. Appendix 3 - Comparison of the Catalogues of AQUAEXCEL3.0 and EMBRC.....	0
5.4. Appendix 4 - AQUASERV Catalogue (version 1)	3

1. Executive Summary

One of the tasks of WP7 is to design, maintain and update the Catalogue of services of the Transnational and Virtual access programme of the AQUASERV consortium (task 7.1. “Catalogue of Services and TA application platform”). The AQUASERV Catalogue of Services constitutes the entry point for applicants to explore and find information on the integrated and customized services offered within its Transnational and Virtual Access programme, to be launched during the Open Call in M6 of the project (September 2024). This deliverable defines the first version of the AQUASERV Catalogue of Services (from now on “AQUASERV catalogue” or “the Catalogue”). The Catalogue will be further developed during the project. A second version will be the object of a following deliverable (D7.2), due in M30 (September 2026).

2. Introduction

2.1. Background

The Transnational Access programme is a competitive funding scheme that allows European and international professionals in the research field to obtain free-of-charge use of research facilities (made available by the beneficiaries of an European project) to run proof-of-concept or more mature experiments of their own research line. Participation in a Transnational Access programme is possible through submitting a research proposal, which is evaluated at a technical level and for scientific quality by a panel of experts.

The catalogue of services lists the services made available for access (on-site, remote, and virtual) by the project beneficiaries participating in the Transnational (TA) and Virtual Access (VA) programmes.

2.2. Aim of the deliverable

Launching the Transnational (TA) and Virtual Access (VA) programme of the AQUASERV project relies on designing and implementing the Catalogue of integrated and customised services offered by the project beneficiaries involved in its TA/VA Open Call and Challenge-driven calls. This report provides the first version of the “ontology of the services” (i.e., the Catalogue) of the AQUASERV partners.

2.3. The Catalogue and the Access System

The Catalogue will be hosted in ARIA (<https://aria.services>), the cloud-based system developed and maintained by INSTRUCT-ERIC (University of Oxford, United Kingdom), which will provide a single-entry point to the AQUASERV services to the applicants of the TA/VA programme. The ARIA system was chosen because it is already being used by different European Research Infrastructures (e.g., EMBRC, EUROBioImaging, INSTRUCT) and European projects (e.g., ASSEMBLE Plus, iNext, canSERV, AQUAEXCEL3.0 and its predecessors). ARIA thus provides the advantage that many beneficiaries in AQUASERV (from EMBRC and AQUAEXCEL3.0) are already experienced with its use.

2.4. Updates of the catalogue and next versions

The Access Officer will maintain and regularly update the AQUASERV Catalogue, with input from the Access Managers (i.e., responsible persons at the beneficiaries involved in the Transnational and Virtual Access programme). A second version of the Catalogue will be published in M30 (September 2026), which will then include new and customized services developed in WP3.

3. Description of work

The services provided by the AQUASERV partners are described in detail in the Grant Agreement, as part of the description of each work package related to Transnational (from TA1 (WP8) to TA26(WP34)) and Virtual Access (from VA1 (WP35) to VA3 (WP37)). These services are grouped (and costed) in 82 “installations” in the Grant Agreement (see Grant Agreement, Part A, p. 103–107).

To provide the best possible user experience to the applicants to the TA / VA programme, a customised service catalogue was created by grouping services of the same “type” in different categories, rather than creating a catalogue by simply listing the number of “installations” available in the Grant Agreement. This organisation, divided into categories, provides a more precise overview of the services available, particularly given that some installations group different types of services from the same partner. This choice also results in a better description of the range of services a given partner offers and highlights the diversity of experimental settings that the user can explore. With the aim to reduce the intricacy of the services information in the Grant Agreement and organize the diversity of “types of services” available in the AQUASERV consortium in more “user-friendly” categories, a first draft of the Catalogue was created by following a series of steps:

1. Analysis of the existing services catalogues
2. Grouping of similar services
3. Structuring of the services in categories and sub-categories
4. Revision of the nomenclature to fit a “service-based” approach

5. Final revision of the catalogue

Below, we provide a description of each step to explain the work done in more detail.

3.1. Analysis of the existing services catalogues

With very few exceptions, almost all the partners of the AQUASERV consortium are affiliated with European Research Infrastructures (see Figure 1), with an established catalogue of services organized in a specific “service ontology” (i.e. the structure, organization and naming of different type of services). These existing catalogues and associated ontologies thus had to be carefully consolidated to create a common Catalogue for the AQUASERV programme.

The design of the Catalogue started with a thorough analysis of the existing service catalogues of the Research Infrastructures involved in AQUASERV (AnaEE, AQUAEXCEL3.0, EMBRC, ELIXIR, and METROFOOD). The partner UGE (affiliated with the research infrastructure RISIS) has not been included in the analysis as it does not provide services in the Transnational Access programme.

Research Infrastructures and partners

Fig. 1. Number of partners in the AQUASERV consortium and their affiliation to European Research Infrastructures.

Please note: Six partners share an affiliation with two or more RIs.

The majority of consortium partners are affiliated with AQUAEXCEL3.0 and EMBRC (33 partners collectively, see Figure 1), so the backbone of the Catalogue was drafted based on the “ontologies” of these two catalogues.

The catalogue of services of AQUAEXCEL3.0 consists of 55 types of services (see [Appendix 1](#)), focused on services for aquaculture (freshwater and marine).

EMBRC's catalogue of services consists of 24 types of services, focused on marine biology and ecology. The catalogue is organised into categories and sub-categories (see [Appendix 2](#)).

The services offered by AnaEE, ELIXIR and METROFOOD were added in the following step (see paragraph [“Organization of services in categories and sub-categories”](#)).

3.2. Grouping of similar services

The catalogue was created through an iterative approach consisting of the following steps:

1. Identifying similar types of services from the catalogues of AQUAEXCEL3.0 and EMBRC
2. Merging similar types of services
3. Creating new service categories based on the merged types of services
4. Analysing the number of occurrences of a type of service of the AQUAEXCEL3.0 catalogue
5. Inclusion of type of services of other partners

1. Identifying similar types of services from the catalogues of AQUAEXCEL3.0 and EMBRC

The catalogues of AQUAEXCEL3.0 and EMBRC share similarities in the type of services. Corresponding services are for example:

AQUAEXCEL service	EMBRC service (corresponding)
Absorbance and Fluorescence Spectrometry	Imaging
Culture facilities for algae	Culture collections
Genotyping and gene expression	Molecular biology and omics
...	...

The analysis of similar categories between the AQUAEXCEL3.0 and EMBRC approaches was iterated to find correspondences between the two catalogues for each of the 55 types of services of AQUAEXCEL3.0.

2. Merging similar types of services

Similar types of services between the catalogues of AQUAEXCEL3.0 and EMBRC were merged into single categories. When appropriate, the category received the name already attributed by either RI. Alternatively, an adequate new name for the service category was created.

3. Creating new service categories

Whenever a type of service was not present in one of the two catalogues, a new type of service was created in the AQUASERV Catalogue (see [Appendix 3](#), and the label “new service” in column “validation”).

4. *Analysing the number of occurrences of a type of service of the AQUAEXCEL3.0 catalogue*

The number of occurrences of a given type of service within the AQUAEXCEL3.0 catalogue (see [Appendix 3](#)) was considered to indicate its relevance for the AQUASERV catalogue. Services occurring only once or twice were not considered relevant for inclusion in the AQUASERV catalogue. Conversely, services that occurred frequently were regarded as highly relevant for inclusion.

5. *Revision of the current categories and inclusion of of service types of other partners*

The resulting preliminary catalogue was further refined to include services of other partners (i.e. those not in AQUAEXCEL3.0 and EMBRC). To this end, the service descriptions provided in the Grant Agreement were checked against the new Catalogue ontology. While the services offered by AnaEE were already covered in the new Catalogue ontology, it has been found that some services by METROFOOD were not represented. We consulted with METROFOOD partners via videoconference calls and emails to receive feedback on the preliminary catalogue and ensure the accurate representation of METROFOOD services. Based on these conversations, it was decided to create a category for food quality analysis, which groups the services of several partners within and outside METROFOOD.

3.3. Organization of services in categories and sub-categories

The types of services resulting from the consolidation process resulted in 47 services (hereafter “service sub-categories” or “sub-categories”). These 47 sub-categories were further organized in 13 higher-level groups (hereafter “categories”). The refined list of services is provided in [Appendix 4](#). The organization of the services in a “two-level” system was chosen to simplify navigation through the final list of 47 sub-categories and guide them to the most suitable service. This choice is also compatible with the layout of the ARIA service catalogue.

3.4. Revision of the vocabulary to fit a “service-based” approach

During the drafting of the Catalogue, special care was taken to ensure that the service nomenclature highlighted the technology and equipment used (e.g. “Mass spectrometry”, “Microscopy and imaging”, “Wet processing lab”, etc.), rather than the scientific applications (e.g. eco-physiology, culturomics, fish physiology) which the given service can be used for. The primary reason for this decision was to allow the applicants to find and choose the type of scientific equipment required for their project while avoiding the risk of deterring users that might fall outside the most common scientific fields or applications typically conducted at any given access provider. However, where appropriate or necessary, the available

scientific expertise associated with a service will be provided in the descriptions of the service, which will also include typical examples of the scientific activities carried out at a given access provider.

The emphasis on methodology and technology rather than application and scientific field may result in a more diverse use of a given service/facility/equipment by Transnational Access users, thus diversifying and expanding the research conducted and facilitating cross-pollination of scientific projects among AQUASERV partners. Each partner's technical expertise and scientific key selling point will be part of the TA handbook so that the applicants can make an informed choice of the required partner, their facilities, and their scientific expertise.

3.5. Final revision of the catalogue

The list of services identified following the approach described above was revised and validated through input received by all access managers in a targeted meeting organized in June 2024.

Subsequently to the presentation of the first draft of the catalogue, a service mapping activity within the community of access managers in AQUASERV was conducted asynchronously via spreadsheets and emails. The aim of this mapping activity was to (1) remove the services subcategories not offered by any access provider/partner and (2) add service sub-categories that were missing from the initial draft. The first version of the AQUASERV catalogue is provided in [Appendix 4](#).

4. Conclusions

With the help of the Access Managers, the Access Officer has prepared a Catalogue of Services to be included in the ARIA access system. The final catalogue consists of 47 service sub-categories ([see Appendix 4](#)) and is organized in the following 13 categories:

- Culture and rearing facilities
- Fieldwork, ecosystem access, and telemetry
- Feed manufacturing
- Taxonomic services
- Disease infection facilities
- Experimental facilities
- Microscopy and imaging
- Biochemical and structural analysis
- Molecular biology and omics
- e-services

All service categories, sub-categories, and service descriptions will be available in the:

- ARIA access system
- TA handbook
- Webpage of the Transnational Access

4.1. Next steps

The improvements foreseen at the moment for the second version of the catalogue are the following:

- adding a catalogue of the available bioresources at each access provider
- adding new and customized services developed in WP3.

5. Appendices

5.1. Appendix 1 - Catalogue of services of AQUAEXCEL3.0

Type of service	Occurrences
Temperate research facility	20
Warm water research facility	16
Biochemical analysis	13
Histology	12
Genotyping and gene expression	12
Spectrophotometry	11
Access to facilities	11
Absorbance and Fluorescence Spectrometry	11
Marine site	10
Light microscopy	10
Molecular labs	9
Microscopy and bio-imaging	9
Cell culture	9
Live Cell Imaging	6
Culture facilities for bacteria	6
Flow Cytometry	5
Feed manufacturing	5
Virus purification	4
Structural and chemical analysis	4
Serology	4
Preparation of test vaccines	4
Marine Models	4
Infection facilities (for bacterial challenges)	4
Fluorescent and confocal microscopy	4
Diagnostic labs	4
Data analytic	4

Culture facilities for viruses	4
Bioinformatics	4
System Biology Modelling	3
Sequencing	3
Infection facilities (for challenges)	3
Culture facilities for algae	3
Calorimetry	3
Purification: Protein / Nucleotide	2
Marine Ecosystems	2
Infection facilities (for viral challenges)	2
In-Vivo Modelling	2
In-situ hybridization	2
Electron microscopy	2
Chemical Screening	2
Zebrafish	1
Yeast expression	1
Purification: chromatographic system	1
Proteomic Mass Spectrometry	1
Native Mass Spectrometry	1
Mammalian expression	1
Labelling Mass Spectrometry	1
Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry	1
Insect platform	1
Fish Physiology and Genomics Facility	1
Culture facilities for algae (macroalgae)	1
Cell-free Expression	1
Biobank sample	1
Access to freshwater research facilities	1
Access to Facilities	1

5.2. Appendix 2 - Catalogue of services of EMBRC

Service category	Service subcategory
Ecosystem access	Coastal research vessels
	Sampling equipment
	Scientific diving
	Submersibles
Biological resources	Culture collections
	Biobanks
	Marine model organisms
	Organisms collected in the wild
	Rearing of aquaculture animals
	Taxonomic services
Experimental facilities	Aquaria and tanks
	Climate controlled rooms
	Dry laboratories
	Wet laboratories
	Mesocosms
Technology platforms	Imaging
	Molecular biology and omics
	Bioassays
	Remote sensing and telemetry
	Structural and chemical analysis
E-services	Data analysis tools and software
	Data sets

5.3. Appendix 3 - Comparison of the Catalogues of AQUAEXCEL3.0 and EMBRC

AquaExcel3.0 service	EMBRC service	AQUASERV service (subcategory)	Occurrences in the AQUAEXCEL3.0 catalogue	validation
Absorbance and Fluorescence Spectrometry	Imaging	Absorbance and Fluorescence Spectrometry	11	ok
	Bioassays	Bioassays	0	new service
Biobank sample	Biobanks	Biobanks	1	ok
Biochemical analysis	Structural and chemical analysis	Biochemical analysis	13	ok
Bioinformatics	Data analysis and software	Bioinformatics	4	ok
Calorimetry	-	Calorimetry	3	ok
	Coastal research vessels	Coastal research vessels	0	new service
Culture facilities for bacteria	Culture collections	Culture facilities for bacteria	6	ok
Culture facilities for algae (macroalgae)	Culture collections	Culture facilities for macroalgae	1	ok
Culture facilities for algae	Culture collections	Culture facilities for microalgae	3	ok
Culture facilities for viruses	Culture collections	Culture facilities for viruses	4	ok
Data analytics	Data analysis and software	Data analytics	4	no
Electron microscopy	Imaging	Electron microscopy	2	ok
Feed manufacturing	-	Feed manufacturing	5	ok
Flow cytometry	Imaging	Flow cytometry	5	ok
Fluorescent and confocal microscopy	Imaging	Fluorescent and confocal microscopy	4	ok
Genotyping and gene expression	Molecular biology and omics	Genotyping and gene expression	12	ok
Histology	Dry laboratories	Histology	12	ok
In-situ hybridization	Molecular biology and omics	In-situ hybridization	2	ok
Infection facilities (for bacterial challenges)	Aquaria and tanks	Infection facilities for challenge trials	4	ok
Infection facilities (for challenges)	Aquaria and tanks	Infection facilities for challenge trials	3	ok
Infection facilities (for viral challenges)	Aquaria and tanks	Infection facilities for challenge trials	2	ok

Insect platform	-	Insect rearing farm	1	ok
Light microscopy	Imaging	Light microscopy	10	ok
Purification: chromatographic system	Structural and chemical analysis	Liquid and gas chromatography	1	ok
Live cell imaging	Imaging	Live cell imaging	6	ok
Mammalian expression	-	Mammalian expression	1	to validate
Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry	Structural and chemical analysis	Mass Spectrometry	1	new service
Labelling Mass Spectrometry	Structural and chemical analysis	Mass Spectrometry	1	new service
Native Mass Spectrometry	Structural and chemical analysis	Mass Spectrometry	1	new service
Proteomic Mass Spectrometry	Structural and chemical analysis	Mass Spectrometry	1	new service
	Mesocosms	Mesocosms	0	new service
Preparation of test vaccines	-	Preparation of test vaccines	4	ok
	Scientific diving	Scientific diving	0	new service
Sequencing	Molecular biology and omics	Sequencing	3	ok
Serology	Dry laboratories	Serology	4	ok
Spectrophotometry	Imaging	Spectrophotometry	11	ok
System Biology Modelling	Marine model organisms	System Biology Modelling	3	ok
	Taxonomic services	Taxonomic services	0	new service
Temperate research facility	Climate controlled rooms	Temperate research facility	20	ok
Virus purification	-	Virus purification	4	ok
Warm water research facility	Aquaria and tanks	Warm water research facility	16	ok
	Wet laboratories	Wet laboratories		new
Yeast expression	-	Yeast expression	1	to validate
Structural and chemical analysis	Structural and chemical analysis		4	no
Chemical screening	Structural and chemical analysis		2	no
Purification: Protein/Nucleotide	Structural and chemical analysis		2	no
Molecular labs	Molecular biology and omics		9	no

Cell-free expression	Molecular biology and omics		1	no
Marine Models	Marine model organisms		4	no
Zebrafish	Marine model organisms		1	no
Microscopy and bio-imaging	Imaging		9	no
Fish Physiology and Genomics Facility	Dry laboratories, Molecular biology and omics		1	no
Diagnostic labs	Dry laboratories		4	no
Marine ecosystems	Coastal research vessels, Scientific diving		2	no
Cell culture	Climate controlled rooms		9	no
Access to facilities	-		12	no
Access to freshwater research facilities	-		1	no
Marine site			10	no
In Vivo Modelling			2	no

5.4. Appendix 4 - AQUASERV Catalogue (version 1)

Category	Sub-category
Culture and rearing facilities	Culture facilities for bacteria
	Culture facilities for macroalgae
	Culture facilities for microalgae
	Culture facilities for zooplankton
	Culture facilities for viruses
	Insect rearing farm
	Culture facilities for fish and invertebrates
Fieldwork, ecosystem access, and telemetry	Coastal research vessels / Boats
	Scientific diving
	Telemetry
	ROVs and underwater video
	Environmental monitoring and sampling
Feed testing and production	Insect meal production
	Live feed experiments
Food & feed quality and packaging	Food & feed quality
	Food traceability
	Food packaging safety
Taxonomic services	Taxonomic services
Biobanks	Biobanks
Disease infection facilities	Infection facilities for challenge trials
Experimental facilities	Mesocosms and artificial ecosystems
	Recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS)
	Wet processing laboratories
	Dry processing laboratories
	Climate-controlled rooms
Microscopy and imaging	Absorbance and Fluorescence Spectrometry
	Electron microscopy
	Flow cytometry

	Fluorescent and confocal microscopy
	Light microscopy
	Live cell imaging
Chemical and biochemical analysis	Bioassays
	Biochemical and biogeochemical analysis
	Calorimetry
	Liquid and gas chromatography
	Serology
	Mass spectrometry
	NIR-Spectroscopy
Molecular biology and omics	Genotyping, genomics, selective breeding
	Sequencing
	Cell transplantation
	In-situ hybridization
e-Services	Bioinformatics
	System Biology Modelling
	Spatial planning
	Datasets
Behaviour and welfare monitoring	Behaviour and welfare monitoring